

Ru^{III} and Ir^{III} and BTATCH has been found useful in the presence of other platinum metals and various base metals.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss PMQ II spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements. A Systronics pH meter equipped with glass and calomel electrodes was used for pH determinations.

Ruthenium chloride hydrate and iridium chloride hydrate solutions were prepared in dilute HCl and standardised³. Standard solutions of the other metals were prepared by dissolving their salts in distilled water or dilute HCl. Hydrochloric acid and 10% sodium acetate solution were employed for regulating of acidity of the solutions. A $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ BTATCH in ethanol was used. All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. BTATCH was obtained as condensation product of thiocarbohydrazide⁴ with thiophene-2-aldehyde⁵. The reagent was prepared following the reported method⁶.

Procedure :

Ruthenium : To an aliquot of ruthenium solution mixed with concentrated HCl (1–2 ml) was added BTATCH solution (10–12 ml) and the solution was heated on a boiling water-bath for 10 min, then cooled to room temperature. The solution was made upto 25 ml with a mixture of ethanol, HCl, and water so that the final strength of solution was 0.3–0.7 *N* with respect to HCl containing 40% ethanol. The absorbance of the pink coloured solution was measured at 540 nm against distilled water.

Iridium : To an aliquot of solution containing upto 51 μg of iridium, ten-times molar excess of BTATCH in ethanolic solution was added and the pH was adjusted to 5.6–6.6 with sodium acetate and HCl. The mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for 30 min, then cooled to room temperature and ethanol (5 ml) was added and mixed well. The deep yellow iridium-BTATCH complex was extracted with ethyl acetate (3×5 ml). The combined extract was dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and the volume made upto 25 ml. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 380 nm against reagent blank.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Ruthenium(III) and Iridium(III) using Bis(thiophene-2-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone as a Sensitive and Selective Complexing Agent

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SEVERAL chromogenic reagents¹ containing $-NH-CS-NH-$ and $-CS-NH-N$ groups have been proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of ruthenium and iridium². In the present communication, bis(thiophene-2-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone (BTATCH), has been recommended as a sensitive and selective reagent for both

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of ruthenium complex show an absorption maxima at 540 nm and the complex in 40% ethanol is stable for 12 h. The iridium complex exhibits an absorption maximum at 380 nm, and the complex in ethyl acetate is stable for 24 h.

For ruthenium-BTATCH complex, maximum and constant absorbance was obtained in 0.3–0.7 *N* HCl medium, below which complete complexation is not possible and above which the absorbance

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deteriorates. The maximum absorption of the iridium-BTATCH complex at different pH was obtained at 380 nm indicating formation of only one complex under the condition. Maximum and constant absorbance are attained in the pH range 5.6-6.6, above which the absorbance is insignificant.

Nature of the complexes : The composition of the ruthenium-BTATCH complex could not be determined by any conventional spectrophotometric methods. For the maximum formation of the coloured complex, 33-fold molar excess of the reagent is necessary.

The empirical formula of the iridium-BTATCH complex was determined by the mole-ratio method⁷ and verified by conventional slope ratio method. The composition of the complex was found to be 3 : 1 with respect to reagent-metal. The composition of the iridium complex in ethyl acetate extract was also determined by solvent extraction technique⁸. The dependency of extraction of iridium on extractant concentration⁹, i.e. plot of log *D* (distribution coefficient) against log [BTATCH] at constant pH, produces a straight line with slope 3, which is in agreement with the results obtained by the earlier investigations.

Beer's law, molar absorptivity and sensitivity : Beer's law is obeyed over the range 0.7-3.5 ppm of ruthenium. The molar absorptivity is $1.6 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandell's sensitivity is $0.0062 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$; where as for iridium-BTATCH complex the optimal concentration range is 1.2-

4.2 ppm, molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are $3.2 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0060 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ respectively.

For 5 parallel determinations of 2.8 ppm of ruthenium, the relative mean error and standard deviation are 0.84% and 0.032% respectively and similarly for 4.0 ppm of iridium the respective figures are 1.2% and 0.08%.

Effect of foreign ions : The effects of a number of foreign ions on the spectrophotometric determination of ruthenium and iridium with BTATCH were studied and the results are recorded in Table 1.

Determination of Ru and Ir in synthetic mixtures : In order to confirm the usefulness the proposed method was applied for the determination of Ru and Ir in various synthetic mixtures of platinum metals. The results are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 1—EFFECTS OF FOREIGN IONS ON THE DETERMINATION OF Ru AND Ir

Ions	Amount of ion added ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) ^a	
	Ruthenium (Ru=2.84 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Iridium (Ir=3.07 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)
Ti ⁴⁺	40	40 ^a
V ⁵⁺	60	40 ^a
Cr ³⁺	40	60 ^a
Mn ²⁺	60 ^a	60 ^a
Fe ³⁺	40	40 ^a
Co ²⁺	80	40
Ni ²⁺	40	40 ^a
Cu ²⁺	12 ^a	20
Zn ²⁺	100	60 ^a
Cd ²⁺	40	40 ^a
Mg ²⁺	40 ^b	20 ^c
Pb ²⁺	40	40 ^a
Bi ³⁺	40	40 ^a
Sb ³⁺	20 ^b	40 ^b
Au ³⁺	20	12 ^a
Mo ⁶⁺	40	40 ^a
W ⁶⁺	60	40
U ⁶⁺	40	40 ^a
Os ⁸⁺	20 ^d	10 ^d
Pd ²⁺	40 ^b	40 ^b
Rh ³⁺	40	10 ^b
Ru ²⁺	—	14
Ir ³⁺	60	—
Pt ⁴⁺	20 ^d	10 ^d

^aWhich caused an error less than 2%.
^bIn presence of EDTA. ^cIn presence of tartarate. ^dPrior extraction with ethylacetate in presence of reagent. ^eIn presence of KI. ^fPrior reduction with sulphurous acid.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Ru AND Ir IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES^a

Sl. no.	Composition of mixture (in μg)	Metal ion found (μg)	Relative mean error %
1. ^a	Ru ^{III} (71.48) + Pd ^{II} (240) + Rh ^{III} (193.16) + Os ^{VI} (225.0) + Ir ^{III} (225.6) + Pt ^{IV} (90.00)	Ru ^{III} (71.20)	0.31
2. ^b	Ir ^{III} + Pd ^{II} (240) + Rh ^{III} (64.38) + Ru ^{III} (71.48) + Os ^{VI} (100.0) + Pt ^{IV} (90.00)	Ir ^{III} (75.94)	0.66
3. ^c	Ru ^{III} (71.48) + Ir ^{III} (76.68)	Ru ^{III} (71.14) Ir ^{III} (76.42)	0.31 0.28

^aAverage of five determinations. ^bPrior extraction of Pd at pH 2-3 with the reagent and reduction of Pt^{IV} with sulphurous acid—then the usual procedure for Ru was followed. ^cPrior extraction of the interfering metals at pH 2-3 in cold condition. ^dDetermined separately as usual.

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